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**ANALYSIS OF SPEED ABILITIES AMONG FOOTBALL AND
HOCKEY PLAYERS OF MANIPUR UNIVERSITY**

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Abstract:

The main purpose of this study was to analysis of speed abilities among football and hockey players of Manipur University. In this study, a total 30 players were selected as subjects randomly (each game 15 players i.e. Football and Hockey) from Manipur University who are participated in national level competitions, and age range between 20 to 25 years. For this study, 50 meters dash run was employed to collect data. The collected data was analysed in the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) Version 21 platform by using descriptive statistic and independent t-test at a level of significance of 0.05. However, the results of the study showed that there was an insignificant difference in speed abilities between football and hockey players.

Keywords: Speed, Football, Hockey, Players

1.1 Introduction:

Sports involve all types of physical activity, typically competitive, that attempts to use, maintain or improve participants' physical skills and abilities while entertaining spectators or other participants. There exist different kinds or forms of sport where competition takes place either in team or individually. Physical athleticism or dexterity plays a major role in determining sport performance. Sports are typically governed by a set of rules or conventions that allow for consistent adjudication of the winner and ensure fair competition. Physical actions like scoring goals or being the first to cross a finish line can determine a winner, as can the decision of judges who evaluate various aspects of an athletic performance, including both

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objective and subjective criteria like technical proficiency or aesthetic impression. Sport is a significant source of entertainment for those who do not participate in it, as spectator sports draw big crowds to venues and are transmitted to a larger audience (Nallella, S. 2014.).

According to Hardayal Singh, physical fitness-including strength, speed, endurance, flexibility, and a variety of coordinative skills-plays a significant role in how well athletes perform in competition. Sports training's primary goal is to develop physical fitness or motor skills because sports are physical activities that cannot be performed without these qualities. Strength and stability of the musculoskeletal system are increased when general health and biological processes are improved. Sportsmen who possess these are said to have particular physical fitness (Singh, H. 1984).

Football is the world's most popular team game. Modern football is very fast by its nature, the spectators and the players enjoy the game. Nowadays with the demand for "high sports performance" the concept of football has been changed. The concept of football has applied skill, technical, tactical development, development of all-important motor components and physiological parameters which are closely associated and contributes to performance in football. Not only technical, physiological development, the sports scientists are also making efforts to develop the intellectual ability of the football players. As in the literature, it has been shown that endurance, speed, agility, maximum leg strength, upper body strength, leg power, muscular endurance, flexibility, coordination and reaction time are important prerequisites for efficient football performance (Singh L Santosh et.al. 2018).

India has regarded hockey as its national sports ever since the country won the Olympic hockey championship in 1928 in Amsterdam. Modern hockey is fast-paced, physically demanding sports that required players to have high level of motor components skill as well as anthropometric exercise, specifically on artificial turf. Many hockey experts believe tall, well-built full backs will benefit the team in the sports of hockey. Hockey players motor fitness is not a brand-new topic, and understanding its components will help you comprehend its intricacy. It is challenging to emphasise any one of this factor of motor fitness components independently because they are interrelated and each contribute to an important element of physical fitness of a hockey player (Belano, A.L. 1996).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The statement of the problem was to find out the *“Analysis of Speed Abilities Among Football and Hockey Players of Manipur University”*.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to analysis of speed abilities among football and hockey players.

2. Methodology

2.1 Selection of Subject:

For the purpose of this study, 30 male players were selected as subjects randomly (Each game 15 players i.e., football and hockey players) from Manipur University who have participated at

national level competitions. The age of subjects was ranged between 20 to 25 years. There were ensured from the health examination that all the subject is medically fit for this study.

2.2 Selection Variables:

The selection of variables was made the followings-

1.Speed

Table – 1 Selection of test

PHYSICAL FITNESS	TEST	CRITERION MEASURES
Speed	50 m Yard Dash	Seconds

3. Administration of the test

➤ 50 m Yard Dash

3.1 Equipment: Stopwatch, whistle, marker etc

3.2 Procedure: Two lines are mark on the ground 50 yards apart. One line is used as a starting line and the other as the finish line. On the signal Ready? Go! the subjects start running at their best speed to reach the finish line at the earliest. The signal ‘Go’ is accompanied with the downward sweep of the starters arm to give the visual signal to the timers who stand at the finish line.

3.3 Scoring: The interval between the starting signal and the instant subject crosses the finish line is the score of the test. The time is recorded correct up to tenth of a second.

4. Statistical procedure for analysis of data

To compare the speed of football and hockey players of Manipur University, the mean, standard deviation, and independent t-test were employed. The level of significance was set at 0.05. Data was analysed by using SPSS Version 21.

5. Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The significant mean difference in the speed abilities between football and hockey players is presented in **Table-1**

Group	Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev	SEM	df	‘t’-value
Football Players	Speed	15	10.28	.61	.157	28	0.912
Hockey Players	Speed	15	10.7	.63	.161		

*Significant at .05 level

$t(0.05) 28 = 2.048^*$

From the findings of the above table, the mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) of the speed abilities of football players is $10.28 \pm .61$ and the mean value of hockey players were $10.07 \pm .63$ respectively (N = 15) for each group. In addition, the standard errors of the mean of hockey players and football players were also found to be .161 and .157, respectively. Hence, there was found an insignificant difference as the value obtained was 0.912 whereas the tabulated value was 2.048 at 0.05 level of significance. This means that football and hockey players have comparable speed abilities.

Figure No.1: Graphical representation of mean and standard deviation difference in speed abilities between football and hockey players.

6. Discussion of findings:

It is evident from the table that there is an insignificant difference among the football and hockey players in speed abilities with regard to the comparison of speed abilities between football and hockey players in Manipur University. Football players have faster speeds than hockey players. The investigator analysed the collected data as per the purpose of the study.

7. Conclusion

It was concluded that there was insignificant difference found in football and hockey players in speed abilities with regard to the comparison of speed abilities among football and hockey players in Manipur University. From this study, it might be concluded that football players perform better quality in speed abilities.

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